

1,4,8,11-Tetramethyl-1,4,8,11-tetra-azacyclotetradecane, a Macrocyclic Ligand with Interesting Properties

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1,4,8,11-Tetramethyl-1,4,8,11-tetra-azacyclotetradecane (TMC) gives with transition metal ions pentacoordinate complexes, which show interesting and peculiar properties. The chemistry of these species $M(TMC)L^{n+}$ is governed by several factors. So the stability constants $K_{M(TMC)L}^L$ strongly depend on the structural and electronic features of L. Linear ligands with π -acceptor properties, such as N_3^- , SCN^- , OCN^- or small ligands such as H_2O , OH^- , F^- are especially well coordinated, whereas larger species such as imidazole or pyridine do not bind. This stems from the *trans*-I configuration of the macrocycle and from sterical interactions between the aminomethyl groups and the apical coordinated ligand.

Unexpected are also the kinetics of the L replacement, since $Co(TMC)H_2O^{2+}$ shows a relatively slow substitution whereas $Ni(TMC)H_2O^{2+}$ reacts so fast that the kinetics cannot be followed by a normal T-jump instrument. The mechanism of the ligand substitution in the Co^{2+} -system proceeds through an associative mechanism.

When 1979 I came to India to participate to the ICCS organised by Professor D. Banerjee in Calcutta, the country first looked to me somewhat strange, exotic and very different from what I knew. After a few days, when the contact with the people was established, when the way of life became evident and when a certain routine took over, I realised that what was strange, exotic and different for me at the beginning, was just another way of life, another way of thinking with its own rules and its own advantages. I enjoyed this experience very much and now looking at it, I find that some macrocyclic chemistry we did in the last years also went through this process. What at the beginning seemed strange and not intelligible, has in the meantime become more evident and understandable.

When we started our studies on tetra-azamacrocycles we came across 1,4,8,11-tetramethyl-1,4,8,11-tetraazacyclotetradecane (TMC, 1) and its metal complexes, which did not fit into the picture of square-planar or *trans*-octahedral geometry, which is typical for the complexes of the parent compound 1,4,8,11-tetraazacyclotetradecane (Cyclam, 2). The more we studied TMC, the more we realised that

- 1 : $R_1 = R_2 = R_3 = R_4 = CH_3$
 2 : $R_1 = R_2 = R_3 = R_4 = H$
 3 : $R_1 = CH_3, R_2 = R_3 = R_4 = H$
 4 : $R_1 = R_2 = CH_3, R_3 = R_4 = H$

the results were exiting and once we began to understand its chemistry, everything started to look quite

normal. This review covers some of these new and interesting results.

Structural studies :

TMC was described practically at the same time by Barefield's¹ and our group² and we both realised that this ligand gives complexes with new and interesting properties. The absorption spectra of the Ni^{2+} and Cu^{2+} complexes of a series of methylated macrocycles 1, 3 and 4 (Fig. 1) clearly show the difference between the tetramethyl and the other

Fig. 1. Spectra of the Ni^{2+} (top) and Cu^{2+} (bottom) complexes with ligands 1 (a), 3 (b) and 4 (c).

derivatives². If one looks at the effect of the increasing number of methyl groups, one finds that a drastical change takes place when four methyl groups are incorporated. All methyl substituted macrocycles except TMC have spectra typical for a square-planar N_4 or CuN_4 chromophore.

The X-ray structure of $Ni(TMC)N_3^-$ shows that the metal ion is pentacoordinated by the four nitrogens of the macrocycle and the azide ion³. Additional results from the structures of the zinc(II)⁴ and cobalt(II)⁵ species confirm that pentacoordination is the typical geometry for TMC complexes. In all these cases the macrocycle is in the *trans*-I⁶ configuration with the four methyl groups all on the same side of the N_4 -plane and the metal ion displaced from the best plane through the four nitrogens in the same direction as the methyl groups (Fig. 2a). Lifting the metal out of the plane allows the nitrogens to bend back, thus releasing the steric interaction of the four methyl groups and the axial ligand. This effect has been observed in the Ni^{2+} complex of a TMC derivative⁷.

Fig. 2. (a) Structure of $M(TMC)H_2O^{2+}$ in the *trans*-I configuration (b) Proposed structure for the 1:2 '*trans*' outersphere' complex in the substitution reaction of $Co(TMC)H_2O^{2+}$ with unidentate ligands L

To study the geometry of $Co(TMC)^{2+}$, $Ni(TMC)^{2+}$ and $Cu(TMC)^{2+}$ in solution we have measured their absorption spectra in solvents of different polarity and donor strength (Table 1)⁸. The spectral data of $Ni(TMC)^{2+}$ in several solvents, described previously^{1,9}, have been discussed by assuming

TABLE 1—ABSORPTION SPECTRA (nm) OF $Co(TMC)(NO_3)_2$, $Ni(TMC)(ClO_4)_2$, AND $Cu(TMC)(ClO_4)_2$, IN DIFFERENT SOLVENTS

Solvent	Co(TMC) (NO ₃) ₂	Ni(TMC) (ClO ₄) ₂	Cu(TMC) (ClO ₄) ₂
Nujol	472, 545, 708		
Nitromethane	(a)	512	584
Acetone	476, 560	388, 515	588
Methanol	476, 557	392, 513	620
Water	472, 543, 725	394, 512, 650	640
Ethanol	477, 554	392, 505, 655	(a)
DMSO	478, 550, 734	398, 527, 670	642
DMF	484, 552, 725	395, 660	649

(a)≡Not soluble

an equilibrium between a square-planar and a pentacoordinate species. Our additional data are in accordance with this view and show a steady change from the square-planar geometry in poorly coordinating solvents such as nitromethane, acetone and methanol to the pentacoordinate species in better coordinating solvents such as DMF. In solvents with intermediate donor properties such as ethanol, water and DMSO, the observed spectra can be interpreted as a superimposition of the absorption of the square-planar and the pentacoordinate form.

Spectra of Cu^{2+} are generally not so diagnostic for the geometrical environment of the metal ion. However, the shift from 584 nm in nitromethane to 649 nm in DMF for $Cu(TMC)^{2+}$ indicates that good donor solvents interact with Cu^{2+} more strongly than the others. The shift to longer wavelengths is a consequence of the axial binding of the solvent to the copper(II)¹⁰. Whether in poorly coordinating solvents $Cu(TMC)^{2+}$ is present in a square-planar geometry is difficult to decide from the spectroscopic data alone.

In the case of Co^{2+} the absorption spectra in different solvents and the magnetic moment of 4.45 B.M. for $Co(TMC)H_2O^{2+}$ can clearly be interpreted with pentacoordinate high-spin species¹¹. The band shape is nearly constant but small shifts in the absorption maxima indicate that the solvent can coordinate to the Co^{2+} in the axial position. The $Co(TMC)H_2O^{2+}$ complex is remarkable because of its stability against oxygenation. Even at high pH no trace of a binuclear μ -peroxo species is formed when a solution of $Co(TMC)H_2O^{2+}$ is kept in contact with dioxygen⁸. This is in clear contrast with the common chemical experience that Co^{2+} complexes with at least three nitrogen donor atoms rapidly pick up dioxygen¹². It is possible that in this complex pentacoordination of the metal ion stabilises the bivalent more than the trivalent

oxidation state, since only octahedral geometry produces a LFSE large enough for the oxidation to the trivalent ion¹⁸.

The ¹³C nmr and ¹H nmr studies of the Ni²⁺ and Zn²⁺ complexes with TMC indicate fluxional behaviour of species with trigonal bipyramidal structure^{4,9}.

Finally it is interesting to note that beside the Ni(TMC)L²⁺ complexes with *trans*-I configuration, a species with *trans*-III structure can be prepared by direct alkylation of Ni(Cyclam)²⁺ with CH₃I in DMSO¹⁴ and that the *trans*-II arrangement has also been observed¹⁵.

Equilibrium studies :

The spectral data in different solvents, indicating that the metal complexes of TMC are at least in part pentacoordinate and that the solvent can interact with the axial position, induced us to study the complexation of unidentate ligands with M(TMC)²⁺ (Ref. 8). The reaction is described by equation (1), in which the solvent has been omitted,

$K_{M(TMC)L}^L$ is the stability constant of the ternary complex. For Ni(TMC)²⁺ we have studied a large number of ligands, such as N₃⁻, SCN⁻, OCN⁻, OH⁻, F⁻, NH₃, pyridine, imidazole, HPO₄²⁻ and CH₃COO⁻. The values of log $K_{M(TMC)L}^L$ (Table 2) show that the rod-like ligands such as N₃⁻ and OCN⁻ form with Ni(TMC)²⁺ the most stable complexes, whereas pyridine and imidazole are not coordinated at all. This high selectivity stems from two factors: steric interactions and π -acceptor properties. The special structure of the macrocycle

Of course N₃⁻ and OCN⁻ are ideal in both respects being linear, thus having only little steric hindrance with the methyl groups of TMC, and at least in part π -acceptors.

The Cu²⁺ complexes are less stable than those of the other metal ions studied. It is astonishing that Cu(TMC)²⁺ does not hydrolyse up to pH 12, although its hydrolytic tendency is well known, whereas both Co(TMC)²⁺ and Ni(TMC)²⁺ form stable hydroxo species. Especially interesting is the relatively high value of Co(TMC)OH⁺. This is obviously due to the special axial position of the water molecule which hydrolyses in this complex. As shown in Fig. 2a the four methyl groups of TMC are pointing in the direction of the aqua-ligand, so that the coordinated solvent molecule is in a relatively hydrophobic environment.

Kinetical studies :

The species M(TMC)L²⁺ also represent ideal models to investigate the kinetics of ligand replacement in pentacoordinate complexes. The solvent exchange kinetics in Co(TMC)H₂O²⁺ were measured by ¹⁷O nmr line broadening¹⁶. The most interesting result is the relatively low rate for the water exchange with $k_{solv} = 4.2 \cdot 10^4 \text{ s}^{-1}$ and the negative value $\Delta S^\ddagger = -34 \text{ J mol}^{-1} \text{ K}^{-1}$, which is indicative for a greater ordering in the transition state. This might imply that the mechanism of water exchange is associative, in contrast to the results for octahedral complexes such as Co(H₂O)₆²⁺, for which a dissociative path has been found¹⁷.

In the case of Co²⁺ the kinetics of the substitution of the water molecule against L could be studied by stopped-flow technique¹⁸. The proposed reaction scheme allows to fit the ligand—as well as the pH-dependencies (Scheme 1). From the

TABLE 2—STABILITY CONSTANTS $K_{M(TMC)L}^L$ FOR Ni(TMC)²⁺, Co(TMC)²⁺ AND Cu(TMC)²⁺ WITH DIFFERENT UNIDENTATE LIGANDS L AT 25° AND I=0.5 M

M(TMC) ²⁺	OH ⁻ *	OCN ⁻	SCN ⁻	N ₃ ⁻	F ⁻	NH ₃	L**
Ni(TMC) ²⁺	3.72	3.67	(a)	2.50	0.57	1.10	<0.3
Co(TMC) ²⁺	5.28	3.82	3.07	2.57			
Cu(TMC) ²⁺	(b)	1.16	2.14	1.29			

*Calculated from the hydrolysis constants K_a with $pK_w = 13.73$. **Other ligands were pyridine, imidazole, HPO₄²⁻ and CH₃COO⁻.

(a) \equiv Precipitation of Ni(TMC)(SCN)₂. (b) \equiv Not observed up to pH 12.

in the *trans*-I configuration with all four methyl groups on the same as the one, to which the additional ligand L must bind (Fig. 2), induces steric interactions between the methyl groups and the larger ligands such as pyridine and imidazole, so that they cannot coordinate. Since the ligands must bind in the axial position of the square pyramidal structure, it is possible that because of the relatively strong equatorial ligand field of the four nitrogen atoms of the macrocycle an axial π -acceptor is a better ligand than a σ -donor one.

Scheme 1

scheme one can derive equation (2), the meaning of the rate constants being apparent,

$$k = k_{-1} + k_{-2}[L]_{tot} + K_{Co(TMC)L}^L (k_{-1}[L]_{tot} + k_{-2}[L]_{tot}^2) / (1 + K_a/[H^+]) \quad (2)$$

Co(TMC)H₂O²⁺ as well as Co(TMC)OH⁺ are present in the pH region, in which the complexation with L was studied. However, only the aqua-species reacts with L to give a 1 : 1 outersphere complex and, in order to explain the quadratic term in [L], also a 1 : 2 outersphere complex. Both outersphere intermediates then react further to give the product

which is always the ternary species Co(TMC)L^+ . The finding of a 1 : 2 outersphere complex in substitution reactions is interesting but not unique¹⁹. In our case it is probably formed because of the special geometrical situation, in which the metal ion is displaced from the plane of the four nitrogens of the macrocycle in the direction of the four methyl groups (Fig. 2a). Also in this direction the unidentate ligand L is coordinated, thus leaving an empty *trans*-position, which is partially blocked by the two propylene bridges of the six-membered chelate rings, which adopt a chair conformation. It is, however, conceivable that exactly in this region an anionic species can weakly bind or interact with the metal ion, without then being able to replace the apical water molecule (Fig. 2b). In other words, the '*trans* outersphere' complex is a dead-end reaction path. So in the '*trans* outersphere' intermediate a second L in *cis*-position must be involved in order to react and substitute the water molecule.

The rate constants for the forward reaction ($K_0 k_{+1}$) change by a factor of 7 from OCN^- to N_3^- , whereas those of the reverse reaction (k_{-1}) differ by a factor of 100 (Table 3). Since the water exchange proceeds through an associative path¹⁸, it is not possible to use the Eigen-Wilkins formalism²⁰ with a dissociative rate-limiting step to discuss these reactions. To understand this one has to realise that we have here a very special situation. On one side Co^{2+} , a d^7 -system, is the reactive

are pointing in the same direction as the leaving water molecule and the incoming ligand L. This sterically very crowded situation does not allow that the incoming and the leaving ligand can move *trans* to each other as is usually found for an associative path. Possibly these restrictions determine the low reactivity of this system and are responsible for the peculiar kinetics.

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TABLE 3—RATE CONSTANTS OF THE FORWARD AND REVERSE REACTION (1) FOR Co(TMC)^{2+} AT 25° AND $I=0.5 M$

L^-	k_{-1} s^{-1}	k_{-2} $M^{-1} s^{-1}$	$k_1 K_0$ $M^{-1} s^{-1}$	$k_2 K_0 K_0'$ $M^{-2} s^{-1}$	$\log K_M^L(\text{TMC})L$ $M^{-1} (a)$
OCN^-	0.54	27.6	$2.25 \cdot 10^5$	$1.16 \cdot 10^6$	3.62
SCN^-	3.96	1970	$4.88 \cdot 10^5$	$2.43 \cdot 10^6$	3.09
N_3^-	56	2590	$1.56 \cdot 10^6$	$7.21 \cdot 10^6$	2.44

*Calculated from the kinetics fitting; to be compared with the values of Table 2.

centre, which has relatively low tendency to form square-planar species as intermediates and probably therefore does not react by a dissociative mechanism. On the other side the steric situation around the metal ion is extremely unfavourable for an associative path, since the four *N*-methyl groups